

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGWA LUM EPSE YENWONG****FIRST NAME: SYLVIA LYDIA****PROGRAM CODE: DDSD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Deleted:** LUM EPSE YENWONG**Deleted:** TYPE SHORTENED TITLE**Deleted:****Deleted:** ACA-401/**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15)
3. American Versus UK English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-34)
5. Understanding the style of guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-56)

ONBOARDING JOURNEY

1) INTRODUCTION

Exciting and mixed feelings, I finally propose my first Response Paper within my journey toward a Doctorate in Diplomacy and Sustainable Development. In this Response paper, I will present my onboarding journey and experience finalizing the first period within the program.

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When I was notified to start my program, I was looking forward to an immediate introduction to diplomacy and sustainable development basics. Hence, I was surprised to see the detailed onboarding with the student orientation guide and step-by-step details to have a broad overview of what awaits us in the program.

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Introducing students from this stage to key applications like Grammarly and Zotero has been key. I faced challenges navigating Zotero, but the progress has been beneficial so far. I must admit that, in my first period, having a course focused on international academic essay writing was the last thing on my mind. However, within this short period, I have learned a lot and know more is in store for me on this journey.

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2) KEY TAKEAWAYS ON ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

This course has permitted me to understand I have to be intentional about bringing to standards my essay writing skills to align with international requirements. Overall, the course has permitted me to learn the difference in academic essay writing, respecting punctuation marks, focusing either on American or UK English when writing, the risk of plagiarism, using a consistent writing style guide, using abbreviations, expressions and most importantly what to expect from the review done by my supervisor.

Most international students need to write essays and reports for exams and coursework. Yet writing good academic English is one of the most demanding tasks students face. (Bailey 2011)

The issue of language I had overlooked till now, turns out to be key in successfully completing my doctorate program. Learning to use the Grammarly application and automatically formatting my papers to American or UK English form the basis for successful academic writing.

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a) Requirements for Writing a Good Academic Essay

I retain here, that the key factor distinguishing academic essays from others is the fact that they seek to provide the answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas” (EUCLID 2021, P7). Students are advised to have an early start-up in essay writing to permit them to accurately assess the essay question, analyze the issue, and research the topic to develop a good initial plan.

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The advice on coherently organizing ideas and structuring an essay into three main parts (Introduction, body, and conclusion) is very helpful. The body of the essay, which is the main part, should have a series of well-structured paragraphs, each outlining a key idea, arguments, and evidence. I also learned that a new idea should never be developed in the conclusion part of an essay.

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Regarding some rules of thumb for writing a good essay, we have to state our main hypothesis at the beginning and stay focused throughout the essay. Sweeping statements should be avoided while clear writing is encouraged, with a need to support assertions with evidence. Remaining original is also a must for academic essay writing. I understand it is important to use an active voice in academic writing, vary sentence structure, and avoid repetition. Academic essays should use formal language, and be precise and concise.

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It is always better to be clear and use simple language rather than showing off flashy words you aren't sure about and potentially misusing them. (“Nine Basic Ways to Improve Your Style in Academic Writing | Student Learning Center” n.d.)

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b) Punctuations and differences between American Versus UK English

In this section, I learned how to correctly use approaches, brackets, bullet points, colons and semicolons, commas, dashes, hyphens, and full stops, amongst others. It is interesting to note that punctuation marks have to equally be used in context when using American or UK English. Also, some words are pronounced the same but spelled differently from American to UK English.

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A series of examples distinguishing the two types of English is proposed but it is reassuring to know when working on Microsoft Word we can tune settings to focus only on American or UK English to minimize errors and remain coherent.

c) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34).

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In this section of my coursework, I understood the meaning of plagiarism and retained the importance of giving credit to the author, and how to do so. I learned how to use in-text citations, quotations, paraphrases bibliographies, and referencing. However, in an event where information is common knowledge known by all and used by several authors, it is not necessary to cite.

d) Understanding the Style of the guide

I understand for the doctorate programme EUCLID University recommends the Turabian style or Chicago style.

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Turabian is a version of the Chicago style that's specifically designed for students and researchers. If you've been told to follow Chicago style when writing your academic research paper, thesis, or dissertation, it's usually the Turabian guidelines that will be most useful to you (Caulfield 2021)

This section of the coursework provides a detailed rundown on the specificities of Turabian style. I learned how and when to use abbreviations, capitalizations, italics, quotation marks, and compound words to work together. Also, I learned that tables are recommended to present clear and coherent information.

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3) CONCLUSION

I can see academic writing at the international level is a different ballgame; **special efforts must** be made to meet the standards. Going through the module on review provided by the course instructor on previously submitted response papers has given me the needed assurance that I am in the right institution and will deal with experts who will bring my current level to standards.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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Bailey, Stephen. 2011. *Academic Writing: A Handbook for International Students*. 3rd ed. London; New York: Routledge.

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Caulfield, Jack. 2021. "Introduction to Turabian Style | Citations & Formatting." Scribbr. May 28, 2021. <https://www.scribbr.com/chicago-style/turabian/>.

"Nine Basic Ways to Improve Your Style in Academic Writing | Student Learning Center." n.d. Accessed January 18, 2024. <https://slc.berkeley.edu/writing-worksheets-and-other-writing-resources/nine-basic-ways-improve-your-style-academic-writing>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.